

BUSINESS PROCESS RE-ENGINEERING USING BIM TOOLS AND APIS

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Supervisors

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Abstract

Digitalization has been a growing trend in the construction industry for many years. Even though the construction industry has been slow to adopt new processes and technology innovations, digitalization is now accelerating and building information modelling is regarded as its backbone. To adopt new technologies and digitalization, engineering and consulting companies have to re-engineer their business processes.

This work focuses on the re-engineering of the quantity takeoff process. The goal is to digitalize the traditional quantity takeoff process using BIM. The presented business process re-engineering is done adopting existing guidelines, recommendations and methodologies from the experts in the field. First, the existing AS-IS process is captured, modelled and analyzed. Three alternative solutions are proposed and evaluated. The chosen solution for the re-engineered BIM-based quantity takeoff process proposes implementing a new, specialized application software, standardization of process inputs, outputs and workflows, controlled vocabulary and development of custom solutions using Revit API to address specific challenges.

The TO-BE process is defined, modelled and implemented through a variety of developments. The reengineered process is successfully applied to a case study of an existing project following the defined TO-BE process model, accommodating all critical success factors. The whole process was executed in a single, digital environment. The number of model-based items in the bill of quantities increased from approximately 20% in the existing process to approximately 70% in the re-engineered process. While there is still room for continuous process improvement, the analysis of the case study suggests that the re-engineered process is much more reliable, time-efficient, better in managing changes, and the overall process control is improved.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-AndrazStarc-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/kFCN1opJSdE>

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